

MADITRACE

Communication & Dissemination Plan

Deliverable D5.1

Version N°6

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Summary

The present communication and dissemination plan (D5.1) outlines the approach, objectives and targets for the communication and dissemination activities to be implemented in the HORIZON-RIA funded “MaDiTraCe: Material and digital traceability for the certification of critical raw materials” project, hereinafter referred to as MaDiTraCe. A new international project contributing to enlarge and integrate the portfolio of technological solutions for traceability and certification of responsible and sustainable raw materials supply chains into a digital product passport (DPP which is compatible with the EU Battery Passport).

The main purpose of this deliverable is to define the scope of communication and dissemination actions that need to be implemented within the project to meet the project’s objective. It is structured in the following way: at the beginning, an introduction includes the purpose, partners contribution and the relation to other activities. Then, the main objectives and strategy related to public communication and dissemination in MaDiTraCe are described, after that the management is included. It further presents the project’s branding and their components. Next chapters cover the online channels and tools focused on communications materials and press bureau. The Awareness raising campaign is included in the following chapter followed by the dissemination channels and contents. Lastly the monitoring and KPIs to analyse all the data are provided.

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EU	European Union
EIT RM	European Institute of Innovation and Technology - Raw Materials
MaDiTraCe	HORIZON-RIA project: Material and digital traceability for the certification of critical raw materials
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month (of the project)
OA	Open Access
PR	Public Relations

Q&A	Questions and Answers
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Raw Materials
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present document D5.1 Communication and dissemination plan (M3), is included in the WP5 Communication, dissemination, exploitation & business case.

The purpose is to describe in detail the means to guarantee maximum communication and dissemination of the MaDiTraCe project results.

To facilitate a more successful implementation of the plan and present the project results to the potential users, this report outlines communication and dissemination objectives, target audiences, channels, messages, activities, evaluation criteria, and the roles and responsibilities of the partnership throughout the duration of the project. It also establishes the visual identity of the project and its main activity, sets up information and communication touchpoints, and provides ideas for communication content. All the actions will be monitored and gathered in a final version of the D5.7 Final event report, at M36.

1.2 Partner contributions

The C&D plan is the project's guidance document for all activities between M1 and M36 of the project and has been developed by ISMC with the contribution of all project partners.

A summary of partner contributions to this strategy within the WP5 can be found in the list below:

T5.1: Dissemination and Communication plan, activities, and events (M1-M36):

- ISMC will develop a Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1, update on M36) containing goals, key target audiences, channels, and KPIs to assess success.
- LGI will develop a visual identity (templates, flyers, roll-up, and virtual backgrounds to promote the project at relevant events)
- LGI will design a project website (M3) to serve as the main digital tool for promoting the project.
- EIT RM will design the awareness campaign to give visibility to the project and results through 5 videos and 2 webinars.
- DMT will lead the press bureau as communications interface to media.

T5.2: Exploitation strategy & business case (M1-M36):

- DMT will lead the initial exploitation strategy plan that will be developed in M3.
- It will be regularly updated during the project by all MaDiTraCe partners.

T5.3: Clustering (M1-M36):

- ICAMCYL will organize 3 clustering events with other relevant projects, initiatives, and organisations.
- All the partners and coordinators from other projects will be invited to contribute to sessions organised together with the MaDiTraCe events with the aim of generating new ideas.

T5.4: MaDiTraCe knowledge-transfer program (M1-M36):

- EIT RM will lead the knowledge transfer and e-learning activities among the projects.
- EIT RM will develop 5 short training videos and 2 webinars, guideline, and summary documents to support outreach.

T5.5: Integration with Smart Specialisation Strategies & Platforms (M6-M32)

- A mirroring strategy will be applied to identify similarities and opportunities between regions and targeted industrial sectors, aligning the Smart Specialization Strategies of the participant regions and fostering transnational and interregional innovation and business opportunities.
- Key actors will be invited to an International Workshop (M30) lead by ICAMCYL in which a series of recommendations and findings will be summarised and drafted as a starting point for the preparation of a roadmap of common actions.

1.3 Relation to other activities

The C&D plan implementation is also related to the work undertaken in other WPs. Specifically, the WP that is interrelated directly with the WP5 is the WP1 Assessment of needs and gaps in due diligence. One of the main elements of the WP is the T1.1: Stakeholder Network led by EIT RM that also will be used by WP5 for the C&D activities.

2 Objectives

Initiatives like the EU Battery Regulation and the EU Directive on Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence promote a reconversion and standardization of the increasingly transparent and secure certification schemes in which institutions, companies and society must be involved.

Since MaDiTraCe will develop and integrate technological solutions for traceability and certification into a digital product passport, the strategic communication and dissemination plan will ensure that a continuous communication takes place and will increase the visibility and impact of MaDiTraCe to the audiences.

The overall objective is presented as follows and is aligned with the purpose of the initial proposal:

Boost the benefits of the project and its potential application in the target EU countries -and beyond by increasing synergies and collaborations through networking activities/events with other EU R&I projects and proposing guidelines and training for stakeholders along the value chain.

According to that Core Objective, the plan includes the following specific objectives:

- Ensure effective communication of project messages and activities at local, national and EU level.
- Identify the specific target audiences to address key messages.
- Implement a broad and differentiated set of tools and dissemination channels.
- Identify KPIs, useful for measuring effectiveness and efficiency of the activities

carried out during the project.

- Demonstrate how the project will cooperate with other projects or related initiatives.
- Define how dissemination activities will be managed.
- Help MaDiTraCe partners to correctly implement the communication strategy.

3 Communication and dissemination strategy

At first glance, communication and dissemination activities may appear different in their functions and target audiences, however, both aim to broaden and maximise the impact of MaDiTraCe by informing about the project, its results and possible research outputs, as well as to engage stakeholders and the public throughout the project.

Communication actions aim to broaden outreach and increase visibility by continuously informing about ongoing activities and results of the MaDiTraCe project to its partners, stakeholders and the public using tools such as the website, press releases, social media posts, newsletter, awareness campaigns, materials, and events.

Dissemination activities will bring results to the scientific community as well as to relevant policymakers and standardisation bodies. On a scientific level, dissemination activities will pay particular attention to publication in international scientific peer-reviewed high impact journals and open Access Research Data.

This strategy establishes the creation, implementation and subsequent impact analysis of communication and dissemination actions and, in an initial mandatory phase, the definition of our audiences and the key messages we will utilise.

3.1 Target audiences

The intended impact of this plan refers to the scientific, societal, technological, economic value of the project and therefore, the segmentation of its different audiences will respond to these characteristics. This strategy includes not only the public in general, but also industries in the value supply chain as well as policy makers, among others.

The MaDiTraCe project will address its communication to the following target audiences:

- General public
- Industry Stakeholders
- Scientific community
- Policymakers and global organizations
- Partners and networks
- Media

Communication and dissemination activities will primarily be directed towards these groups and will also utilise the contacts and networks of each of the consortium partners.

To improve the scientific impact of the activities, foster international interactions and receive high quality feedback, MaDiTraCe will establish an Advisory Board (see table 1)

and promote an engaged dialogue between all stakeholders, which in turn will extend this network to representatives of all sub-groups in relation to the battery, magnet, automotive, photovoltaic and microelectronics supply chains.

Name	Added value	Comments
 UN Economic Commission for Europe	Will evaluate MaDiTraCe with respect to SDGs and contextualise the project activities in the international regulatory framework	Develops United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) a universally acceptable and internationally applicable scheme for the sustainable management of all energy and mineral resources. <i>Contact: Harikrishnan Tulsidas, Scott Foster</i>
	Evaluates MaDiTraCe with respect to due diligence needs of automotive industry	Stellantis is a leading global automaker and mobility provider that offers clean, connected, affordable and safe mobility solutions (Brands: Fiat, Chrysler, Opel, Citroën, PSA...) <i>Contact: Seydou Hebie, Nicolas Champetier</i>
	Evaluates and supports MaDiTraCe in IT aspects	IT Plattform provider. <i>Contact: Max Enno Kraft</i>
	Evaluates and supports MaDiTraCe in IT aspects	IT consulting, software services for customers of all industries (e.g. BMW, CreditPlus, Daimler, Deutsche Bahn, Miele, ProSiebenSat.1, SMA Solar and Sonar) <i>Contact: Andre Mundo</i>
	EU perspective on REEs, access to deposit and samples	Rare Earths Norway SAS is involved in the development of the Fen Carbonatite Complex, probably Europe's largest carbonatite-hosted deposit of rare earth elements. <i>Contact: Alf Reistad, Trond Watne, Rune Vigdal</i>
	EU perspectives on unconventional Li sources (geothermal)	Vulcan Energy is aiming to decarbonise the transition to electric mobility, through its world-first Zero Carbon Lithium™ Project for electric vehicle batteries, and its renewable energy business. <i>Contact: Vincent Ledoux Pedailles</i>
	Expertise on Li value chain, Multiplier for MaDiTrace dissemination/implementation	The European Lithium Institute eLi gathers partners along the whole lithium value chain to generate focused international cooperation. By pooling expertise in the fields of exploration, mining, processing, manufacturing and recycling plus predictive modelling. <i>Contact: Andreas Bittner</i>
	Perspective of a mining company	Global mining company already active in traceability issues, e.g., Tracer™ platform for tracking and tracing of diamonds. <i>Contact: Jan Klawitter</i>
	Multiplier for MaDiTrace dissemination/implementation	Competitiveness hub for the subsurface industries. AVENIA has more than 200 members all belonging to the energy and environmental sectors. <i>Contact: Jérôme Gouin, Emmanuelle Robins</i>
	Expertise on material fingerprinting of conflict minerals. Benchmarking of certification schemes	Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources committed to sustainable use of natural resources and protection of the human habitat. As a neutral institution it advises ministries and the European Community and acts as partner in industry and sciences. <i>Contact: Gudrun Franken</i>

Figure 1: Confirmed AB members

3.2 Key messages

To design C&D actions and be successful, it is necessary to adapt the messages accordingly to the audience. Key words will help us to create the initial messages that will be addressed to each target audience (Figure 2) mostly, when publishing content in social media.

Figure 2:Key words by target audience

The strategy will revolve around communication and raising awareness objective about responsibly sourced raw materials. This will be achieved through effective and transparent communication using appropriate language and involving multiple publics. Key messages are described below and will be tailored according to each target audience to achieve effective communication on traceability and certification of sustainable raw materials through a DPP.

All target audiences

- Secure supply of sustainably exploited and processed raw materials is crucial for the development and resilience of European society.
- Sustainable (critical) raw materials are pivotal for EU Green Deal.
- All actors across the value chain (e.g., manufacturers, suppliers, researchers, policy makers, standards organisations) have important roles in RM traceability.
- Different actors' actions shape each other and the perceptions around RM tracing and certification.
- Joint meaning-making and co-creation between actors from various backgrounds can lead to innovative solutions and actions towards sustainable raw materials.

The general public

- Urgent changes are needed to reduce the environmental footprint of RMs.
- Consumers' actions play an important role in leading the way for other consumers', as well other RM actors', actions.
- Frontrunner consumer-citizens and civil-societal actors are needed to spread RM tracing and certification, including through grassroots initiatives.

Industry stakeholders

- Industry actors can contribute to significant changes in how raw materials are sourced.
- RM traceability and certification is a way to enact business sustainability, circular economy, and corporate social responsibility, also being a selling point to customers.
- Manufacturers can impact their customers' and suppliers' RM-related norms and practices through, for example, marketing, labelling, and packaging.
- RM traceability should be addressed on a strategic level.

Scientific community

- Researchers from different fields are needed to find effective solutions for RM tracing.
- New scientific knowledge is needed that other researchers can build upon.

Policymakers and global organisations

- Decision-making regarding RM tracing and certification should be based on the insight gathered from the impact assessment of existing solutions.
- RM tracing and certification contributes to achieving the goals of the CE Action Plan and the EU Green Deal.

Partners and networks

- Cooperation among different RM initiatives and projects is vital.
- MaDiTraCe is open for collaboration between researchers.

Media

- Communicators and media have a significant role in disseminating information on RM tracing and certification.
The ways these issues are addressed in communication, media and education shape the norms around it.

3.3 Timeline

All the key actions of the C&D plan, as well as milestones related to the reports, have been gathered in a timeline diagram that will serve as a roadmap to all partners and that will also be constantly updated.

It must be considered that there are certain activities that will be present from the beginning of the project until its closure and that will take place according to the needs of the project.

Figure 3: Timeline

4 Management

All consortium members will participate in the C&D activities under the direct guidance of the ISMC and under the supervision of the coordinator, BRGM. In addition, all partners shall use their channels for the placement of project news and specialised articles to obtain a higher multiplier effect and to reach an even wider target audience.

4.1 Content flow

In this case, ISMC will collect the information and be responsible for its dissemination, receiving from the partners news, scientific publications, images, or information on events in which the project will participate. The coordinator will monitor all the process and supervise the content.

The collaboration between ISMC and LGI will be essential for the publication of news on the website. ISMC will also be responsible of launching the newsletter with LGI's support.

EIT RM will collaborate in the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy with the creation of five videos, the organisation of two webinars with topics of impact for the project, and the design of an awareness-raising campaign to boost the visibility of MaDiTraCe. These instruments will be addressed specifically further on.

Figure 6: Roles and responsibilities

5 Project Branding

Brand style guide will translate the soul of the project into the design. It also helps with the usage of the brand and advises how to communicate it properly. It will help the relevant stakeholders and the people involved recognize the project and trust its goals. It will be designed in such a way to show the project's personality and support the dissemination of information. The consortium will be empowered by brand style guide and set of instructions on best practices for each component: correct usage of logo variations, logo size and placement, colour palette and proper colour use, typefaces, text, image and photography guidelines, editable templates management, etc.

One of the first actions taken to start building the MaDiTraCe brand was the design of the project's overall visual identity, which includes an official logo, a colour palette, typefaces, and templates adapted to each type of support material. This task has been developed by LGI.

5.1 Logo and visual identity

One of the first communication actions was to develop the project's visual identity. To ensure brand recognition, consistency and a strong project identity, several logo versions were designed and analysed to best represent the project before the kick-off meeting, during which a logo vote was held.

The logo below was chosen based on the results of the vote. It will be associated and included in all paper and electronic documentation as well as promotional materials.

Figure 7: MaDiTraCe logo

The logo mark, a series of interconnected and infinite chain links, takes the shape of an "M," representing the project name as well as the concept of transparency, traceability, and sustainability in CRM supply chains. The green colour is meant to represent sustainability, while the blue represents technology and innovation. The gradient blending the two colours shows the interconnectedness of these key aspects.

Figure 8: Logo variations

One typeface was selected for the project logo. The choice was made based on its readability, universality and overall structure which provides a simple but modern image. The project title uses Korolev Rounded Bold. This font cannot be modified and must be used for the MaDiTraCe logo.

In text, the project should be referred to as MaDiTraCe.

5.2 Rules when using the logo

When using the logo, the following rules will be applied:

- It cannot be modified and must be used on all promotional materials (paper or electronic) related to or produced during the project.
- The MaDiTraCe logo must be used in PNG format with a transparent background or in EPS format (vector option, high definition for printed documents, goodies...).
- All versions of the logo are available for download on the collaborative project workspace.
- When used with other logos, the MaDiTraCe logo size must be proportional to that of other logos.
- For optimal visibility and readability, the logo must be surrounded by a proportional amount of blank space as illustrated below.

Figure 9: Incorrect and correct uses of the MaDiTraCe logo

5.3 Colour palette

To illustrate the sustainability, technology, and innovation aspects of the project, the colours blue, green and a blue/green gradient were used. A dark blue was selected to complement these bright colours and is to be used as a font colour in documents or in visual designs promoting the project.

Figure 10: Colour palette

5.4 Typefaces

The typefaces to be used in documents such as Word, PowerPoint and other desktop applications should be:

- Avenir Next LT Pro in bold for headers and titles:

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
123456789?.,;!/+-@

- Avenir Next LT Pro for body text

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 123456789?.,;!/+-@

On the MaDiTraCe website, the typeface used is Jakarta Sans.

5.5 Information on EU funding – Obligation and right to use the EU emblem.

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise, any dissemination material must indicate that the project received funding from the European Union's. The European Union flag and the sentence "Funded by the European Union" should appear, as it is shown on Figure 10.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 11: EU funding information

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EISMEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them".

5.6 Templates

5.6.1 Project presentation template

A PowerPoint presentation template was designed and distributed to all partners shortly after the start of the project. Easy to use and versatile, the template adds value to the MaDiTraCe brand and ensures the project's visibility when presented at events or conferences.

Figure 12: PowerPoint template

5.6.2 Deliverable template

A Word document template was also prepared and shared with all MaDiTraCe partners shortly after the start of the project. Consistent with the MaDiTraCe visual identity and streamlined for ease of use, the template makes it easy for partners to collaborate on deliverables.

Figure 13: Template guidelines

To ensure consistency across all deliverables and documents, the template includes strict guidelines.

1 First level heading (use style: Avenir Next LT Pro, 18 pt, bold)

Body text: Avenir Next LT Pro, 11 pt

1.1 Second level heading (use style: Avenir Next LT Pro, 16 pt, bold)

Body text: Avenir Next LT Pro, 11 pt

1.1.1 Third level heading (use style: Avenir Next LT Pro, 14 pt, bold)

Body text: Avenir Next LT Pro, 11 pt

1.1.1.1 Fourth level heading (use style: Avenir Next LT Pro, 12 pt, bold)

Body text: Avenir Next LT Pro, 11 pt

For bullet list, use:

- Bullet style of choice

For number list, use:

1. Number style of choice

Figure 1: Example of a figure

(To add hyperlink: Click on References tab and add caption - then choose Figure)

Heading 1	Heading 2	Heading 3	Heading 4

Table 1: Example of a table

(To add hyperlink: Click on References tab and add caption - then choose Table)

Figure 14: Template cover

5.6.3 Agenda template

A Word document template has been created for the organisation of MaDiTraCe events and to be able to share the agenda of the events in a template that facilitates this task and follows the visual identity of the project.

Figure 15: Agenda template

6 Communication channels and tools

In MaDiTraCe, different tools and channels will be used for communication processes (table 1). These will be employed depending on the target audience and the action to be carried out to finally measure the results. The effectiveness of the C&D plan will increase if each tool and channel are used appropriately to address the target audiences in the different phases of project implementation.

Channel & Tools	Purpose	Target audience
MaDiTraCe website	Wide-scale dissemination of project objectives and public results, increased awareness on the societal crucial role of raw materials	All audiences

Social media: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube	Recognition of project and public engagement through social media	All audiences
Standard presentation slides	Standard presentation slides to easily present the project in external events or meetings, in a way that contributes to the project's overall strategy	All audiences
Flyer	Informative material to be distributed at workshops and events organised by MaDiTraCe	All audiences
Banner	Catch the attention of the users and call to action for upcoming activities	All audiences
Newsletters	Dissemination and increased awareness of project results	Related initiatives. NGOs. industry stakeholders, scientific community
Videos	Wide-scale dissemination of project objectives and public results, increased awareness on CRM sector	All audiences

Table 1: Communication channels and tools

6.1 Online channels

6.1.1 Website

The launch of the MaDiTraCe website developed by LGI in M3, constitutes an important milestone for the project www.MaDiTraCe.eu. The hosting of the website will last for the complete duration of project and 5 years after the project's end.

The website is responsive and future-proof. Having these features in mind, the following elementary requirements for EU-funded projects were taken into consideration:

- Modern design - website will reflect the project's discipline and industry while offering a nice display of the information
- Transparency and accessibility - since the content on the website will be accessed by various stakeholders, the website provides information of quality and is accessible
- High responsiveness - to reach as many public as possible, website is accessible via various devices - smartphones, tablets, smart TVs, etc. to maximise impacts and provide meaningful and experience to users

Figure 16: Screenshot of homepage

The website supports the following functionalities.

- Documents available for download on click
- Free word search throughout the website
- Newsletter subscription boxes

- Visually engaging images and design
- Comprehensive and easy-to-understand content
- Direct links to social media accounts

EU funded projects are developing and growing throughout their whole course, and it is considered the importance of the Consortiums being able to further improve and develop the provided solution after the official launch date.

After the initial setup, together with the Consortium will be further identified the needs for further customizations such as:

- Introduction of new custom teasers
- Modification of existing teasers and content elements
- Introduction of new pages and modification of existing ones
- Development of new functionalities

All partners will regularly contribute content and share news and events to support the updating of the website.

6.1.2 Social media

MaDiTraCe aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing its reach-out to target audiences and broad public and ensure an active interaction with them. To ensure maximum usability and exploit to the most possible MaDiTraCe partners' already developed networks in social media, focus has been given to specific platforms, that partners have been using regularly and successfully to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders. The main social network for the project will be the [LinkedIn](#) page, a [Twitter](#) profile, and the [YouTube](#) channel.

LinkedIn has a great potential in terms of connecting with companies, stakeholders, new projects and is the best tool for networking. MaDiTraCe will position its brand through the following objectives:

- Interact with audiences
- Position MaDiTraCe within the sector as a DPP expert
- Create synergies with other projects, stakeholders and companies
- Release the results of the project and generate future actions

We will spread the news published on the website, create call to action to different events organise by MaDiTraCe, such as clustering events or webinars, but also announce those attended by project partners, and content generated by the project. LinkedIn page will publish at least two post per month, follow all the partners and key actors of the sector, and use the trends to boost the page and hashtags based on keywords.

@maditrace www.linkedin.com/company/maditrace/

Figure 17: LinkedIn project page

Twitter profile has been created under the name @maditrace <https://twitter.com/maditrace>

This channel will serve us to create a wider community around the project, disseminate its progress as well as its results. Four main objectives have been established for the strategic use of this social network:

- Connect and establish dialogues with users/audiences
- Spread knowledge about DPP and CRM
- Generate traffic to the project website
- Publicise the project results

The Twitter account will be monitored daily to keep up to date with the latest trends related to MaDiTraCe topics, as well as to meet users who interact with the account. Two tweets minimum per month will be published with information of the project. To retweet content that is of interest to MaDiTraCe and its partners will be also recommended.

Since tweets are indexed by Google, and this favours search engine optimisation, it will be necessary to use the keywords as hashtags.

Figure 18: Twitter project profile

A YouTube channel has been created under the name of @maditrace <https://www.youtube.com/@MADITRACEPROJECT>

This channel will serve us to create a wider community around the project sharing the videos with the target audiences.

Figure 19: Youtube channel

A classification of the types of content is proposed to facilitate social media management and to respond to the objectives of the strategy.

Type of content	Description	Key points
INFORMATIVE	MaDiTraCe Project	Website, flyers, newsletter, press releases, other
DIVULGATION	MaDiTraCe Dissemination	Events organised within the project, participation of partners in external events, awareness campaign, other
EDUCATIONAL	MaDiTraCe Expertise	Scientific knowledge, EU news, partners value, other

Table 2: Types of contents for social media

Partners will be invited to follow and share all the content published in these channels to multiply its impact.

Lastly, a social media Content Plan spreadsheet will be implemented by ISMC to programme and follow up the actions internally.

Channel	Copy	Format (e.g., video, image, text, shared content, link, etc.)	Person in charge	Publication date	Hashtags	Link	Tagged users

Figure 20: Content plan for social media

6.2 Communication materials

6.2.1 Standard presentation slides

Standard presentation slides have been created to allow consortium members to easily present the project in external events or meetings, in a way that contributes to the project’s overall strategy. The standard presentation slides save the consortium members time and provides them with the right tool to deliver an impactful, attractive, and consistent presentation of the project.

Figure 21: Standard presentation slides

6.2.2 Flyer

A flyer was designed and will be distributed at workshops and events organised by MaDiTraCe, as well as at external events. It includes the main message, key words, consortium members and objectives of the project.

The flyer will also be available on the website as a tool to present the project. It can be used as a simple, visual presentation by consortium members who would need to introduce the project to their colleagues or partners.

Figure 22: Flyer

The flyer is eye-catching, connected to the project's brand, with chosen titles and content to drive attention.

6.2.3 Banners

Banners be used on project's website and social media: they play a key role in grabbing the attention of the users and as a call to action for upcoming activities.

Figure 23: LinkedIn banner

The design will be developed to enable the project Consortium to showcase the project. Each banner will be updated if needed to fit the requirements of a specific event based on the consortium's feedback. They help establish a connection with stakeholders, and with

the dissemination of the project data by a combination of text and images according to the visual identity of MaDiTraCe project. Banners in landscape, skyscraper and square sizes will be used as in the example below.

Figure 24: Example of banner

6.2.4 Newsletters

A newsletter template will be created and WP5 will lead the distribution. A newsletter will be issued twice a year (6 total) to disseminate the progress and results of the project. Each newsletter may include an editorial note by the coordinator or one of the partners, a WP highlight, significant milestones, and other project updates.

6.2.5 Videos

EIT RM will produce five animated videos to promote the project's objectives, activities, and results. Two of the five videos will be crucial for the project since they will be used at the time of the project's launch and its closure:

- The first video, which will be published in the first months of the project, will be an animated introduction with general information about the project scope, objectives, and benefits.

Figure 25: Draft of the first video

- Another video will be released at the end of the project life showing the progress and its main results. The main objective is to widely disseminate the public objectives and results of the project and to raise awareness of the Customer Relationship Management sector.

Lastly, during the development of the project, three videos will be used depending on the needs and the key activities to be carried out such as clustering events, awareness campaign or webinars.

This type of media is a simple tool that helps to explain the project to a wider audience and to disseminate its results in a visually appealing way. In terms of storyline, visuals and music, the video will be a dynamic and modern tool to maintain viewer interest and communicate project information, accompanying and aligning with the overall visual identity of the project to support the unified look and feel of the project's branding. Each video will be delivered in *.mp4 format, optimised for viewing on different devices.

6.3 Press Bureau

The Press Bureau lead by DMT will function as communications interface to media of all kinds as well as optimise the content in coordination with the responsible specialists (WPs).

Aims:

- Increase awareness on the MaDiTraCe project (vision, mission, mantras, etc)
- Profiling of project results (TRL specific future services, products, solutions)
- Positioning of selected experts and scientists
- Establishing and maintain relations to selected journalists / media houses

Corner stones:

- PR pitch book: Q&A and key messages from the communication plan are used as content for the PR pitch book
- Press releases distribution, Articles, Opposite-Editorial (Op-Ed)
- Interviews, conferences, webinars
- Press officer as initial contact for media and other third parties
- Online-Media monitoring and reporting on MaDiTraCe project

Guidelines:

- Press releases will be approved by the project coordinator and Press Bureau before publication. Selected and important press releases with big impact must be approved by the Executive Committee.
- The specialists (WP5) create content. The draft versions of the texts (approx. 60% finished) contain the core content and statements of the press release. The drafts are forwarded to the Press Bureau for finalisation.
- The Press Bureau is the only place for the distribution of press releases to avoid multiple address.

Figure 26: First press release

Target audiences:

1. EU-Brussels-Ecosystem
2. Scientific Community
3. Industry Stakeholders
4. Future applicants

Main Target Languages: English, French and Spanish.

Figure 27: Structure of the PR content process

7 Awareness raising campaign

EIT RM has designed an awareness campaign named “In Raw Materials We Trust” to give visibility to the project, specifically, about the digital passport of raw materials. The primary goal of the campaign is raising awareness about the digital product passport to the European society and specialized audiences like industry stakeholders, and therefore to increase public knowledge about the traceability and certification of responsible and sustainable raw materials supply chains.

A mission statement will be created around the message: "MaDiTraCe aims to raise awareness about the origin and traceability in CRM, to encourage people to be informed, and to advocate for an improved certification system across the EU."

The tools and channels to be used in the awareness raising campaign are:

- A press release will be shared in different languages (English, French and Spanish) through the Press Bureau to ensure a larger reach.
- A short video and a flyer will be created with the facts about the campaign using MaDiTraCe communication channels.
- E-learning activities will be employed: two webinars aligned with the campaign.

In social media messages will be easily understandable to facilitate users spread the word and the tag for the campaign #InRawMaterialsWeTrust will be used in every communication. The campaign will be shaped during the project with the collaboration of the involved partners EIT RM, ISMC, LGI and BRGM.

8 Dissemination channels and content

Some tools and channels will be used for dissemination actions on MaDiTraCe (table 3). These will be employed depending on action to be carried out and the target audience in order to measure their results.

Channel & Tools	Purpose	Target audience
Interactions and exchange with other related projects	Synergies with other relevant projects in the sector	Scientific community, industrial stakeholders
Events	Strengthened dissemination and increased awareness of the project among stakeholders	Related initiatives, media, NGOs. industrial stakeholders, scientific community
External event attendance	Awareness of project, closer links with stakeholders, identification of potential collaborations	Related initiatives, NGOs, industrial stakeholders, scientific community
European dissemination channels	EU channels to maximise impact	Related initiatives, NGOs, industrial stakeholders, scientific community, policy makers, general public
Scientific and other publications	Dissemination of results leading to uptake and replication of data for further research	Scientific community, general public, industrial stakeholders

Table 3: Dissemination actions

8.1 Interactions and exchange with other related projects

MaDiTraCe aims to ensure synergies among relevant ongoing projects (Table 2), in coordination with WP1 (through engagement with the stakeholders who will participate in other communication or dissemination initiatives). This goal will be reached through active participation in bilateral discussions and meetings, the exchange of results and deliverables, possible joint dissemination events, and clustering activities with other European and national/regional projects.

This is a continuous task to ensure that selected, relevant results from this project and others will be shared for mutual benefit over time.

Some projects which are under consideration by MaDiTraCe are presented here below. Other projects could replace the following ones, always addressing the most positive impact for MaDiTraCe in terms of dissemination.

Related initiatives	Call	References	Connection with MaDiTraCe
"Battery Passport made with Germany"	German Bundestag	GABZF335	Associated with the initiative of the German Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action "Battery Passport made with Germany" to build a DPP for batteries. Learnings and requirements will be directly processed (via SPHERITY) in MaDiTraCe.
Project(s) selected for CSA call DIGITAL-2021-TRUST-01-DIGIPASS	DIGIPASS	Not applicable	MaDiTraCe will strongly cooperate with the CSA initiative around the DIGIPASS call. MaDiTraCe will reinforce the actions regarding critical raw material transparency and compliance with CERA4in1 standards.
EIT RM project CERA 4in1	EIT RM	Not applicable	MaDiTraCe builds on this base with development of the other sub-standards of the system with the aim of creating a responsible and transparent supply chain in mineral raw materials.
AfricaMaVal	HORIZON EUROPE	GA 101057832	Develops EU-Africa partnership on responsible sourcing of mineral resources for the EU industry while granting a sustainable local co-development. Synergies on upstream sections of CERA4in1 certification, on material traceability via BRGM.
SUSMAGPRO & REEsilience	HORIZON EUROPE	GA 821114 GA 10038960	Both projects focus on the development of novel technologies for the recycling of REE magnets. ULEI is partner in both. Synergies on LCAs, supply chain mapping in WP3 and WP4.
SCREEN	HORIZON 2020	GA 958211	A on developing a CRMs expert network and update the Critical Raw Material factsheets. CEA leads this project and BRGM, ULEI, LGI and EIT-RM are partners. This network will generate useful links for WP1 and WP5.
FUTURAM	HORIZON EUROPE	GA 101058522	Assessment of availability of secondary raw materials in Europe (CRMs). Models of materials flow and stocks for some of EU waste flows with high CRMs potential (electronics, batteries, mining wastes, slags, wind turbines). BRGM is partner. Synergies with WP2, WP3 mapping of secondary resources.
TARANTULA	HORIZON 2020	GA 821159	MaDiTraCe and TARANTULA address key generic subjects such as Social License to Operate and the importance of implementing sustainable and responsible mining practices.

Table 4: Related projects

8.2 Conferences and events

MaDiTraCe will organise events among the project and be present in conferences and events related to the project topics. The organisation and dissemination of events will use the communication channels and tools to reach the specific target audience involved.

The events organised by MaDiTraCe will be:

- Annual workshops (digital and physical) for engaging stakeholders.
- 3 clustering events (around M8 online, M18 midterm event, M35 within final event) will target related initiatives.
- S3 International Workshop (M30) and final event (around M35, organised in France) to present the final results.

In addition, it will be recommended to participate or attend events organized by others. Some international conferences that are under consideration are:

- International Green Week
- European Geosciences Union EGU General Assembly
- Paris Blockchain Week Summit
- European Blockchain Convention
- European Union SuperCluster Finland

8.3 European dissemination channels

MaDiTraCe project will use official EU channels to disseminate the project results with the aim of maximising the impact, allowing other researchers to go a step forward, contributing to the advancement of the state of the art and making scientific results a common good.

The main EU dissemination channels to be targeted are:

- [CORDIS](#): a multilingual magazine for articles and publications based on research results.
- [Horizon Magazine](#): it contains the latest news and features on science that invites thought and innovative EU-funded research projects and innovative EU-funded research projects.
- [Horizon Results platform](#): public platform that hosts and promotes research results thereby widening exploitation opportunities.

8.4 Scientific publications

MaDiTraCe will fully embrace the open access policy of Horizon Europe, favouring Gold Open Access (OA) whenever possible. Open access will also be granted to the metadata that identifies the deposited publication. We will make available all scientific outputs, either in scientific journals or conference proceedings, under OA conditions, by consciously choosing venues and publishers. We will also make use of any OA platform such as Open Access Europe to maximise our outreach. At latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version, or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, will be deposited in a trusted repository (Zenodo, HAL...) for scientific publications - immediate open access is provided to the deposited

publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights.

MaDiTraCe results will be published in various, fully OA interdisciplinary journals. Some examples of targeted OA journals are:

- Science, Nature Earth & Environment
- Resources Policy
- Practice and Policy
- Journal of Responsible Innovation
- Sustainability
- Cleaner and Responsible Consumption
- International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment
- Journal of Geochemical Exploration

Also, we will use the MaDiTraCe website for public reports and OA online repositories such as Zenodo to make our publications accessible.

9 Monitoring & Key Performance Indicators

All C&D activities as part of the MaDiTraCe project will be monitored. ISMC is responsible to implement different tools such as the Data collection for C&D actions (Fig.4) and the social media Content Plan (Fig.20) that allow to oversee and to follow up the communication performance on behalf of the project.

This plan comprises the monitoring of project implementation, putting in place a validation process for the results of the C&D plan. The observations drawn from the monitoring over a specific period allow for a meaningful comparison of findings and results of long-term. MaDiTraCe website and social media can give us the quantitative and qualitative trend of communication activities over time. For that reason, digital platforms such as Matomo, Metricool or the analytic section of the channel i.e. LinkedIn, will help us to analyse metrics, KPIs and insights within the communication channels.

Specifically, to understand how the website is used by visitors, Matomo or a similar GDPR-compliant analytics tool will be employed. Upcoming reports will provide insights regarding:

- How many users visit the website
- Which pages are viewed the most
- Where the majority of viewers are located

These results will enable the communication team to adapt its strategy to be more efficient and reach a wider audience.

9.1 KPIs

KPIs are used in MaDiTraCe to evaluate the success of actions to the extent that they contribute to the achievement of objectives, also to determine whether they are achieving the expected results or corrections are needed.

To carry out a continuous monitoring process, detailed above, the following indicators will be used to measure the output and impact of C&D activities.

Channel	Description	KPIs [month]
Website	Interactive, dynamic, permanent online hub	Live [M3], 10.000 hits [M36]
Social media accounts	Three social media accounts LinkedIn, Twitter and Youtube	Social media accounts are live [M3], at least 500 followers per channel [M36] 500 videos views by [M36]
Press Bureau	MaDiTraCe press-agency: main contact with media	At least 3 Press released by the end [M36]
E-newsletters	A periodical distributed by email to an opt-in list of subscribers	At least 6 e-newsletters to 100 subscribers [M36]
Events	Mid-term event [around M18] (virtual), final event [around M35], S3 international workshop organization [around M30]	200 attendees over three events.
E-learning activities	2 webinars with an educational and informative aim	50 participants between project partners and stakeholders [M36]
External event attendance	Consortium partners will actively promote the project, its objectives and results at relevant external events through oral and poster presentations	Representation at 12 conferences and external events [M36]
Scientific and other publications:	Consortium partners will promote the project, its objectives and results by way of written publications, such as scientific publications and articles in the popular and specialist press and blogs, ensuring OA	14+ publications [M36]

Table 5: Main KPIs

The KPIs analysis and the monitoring process of the C&D activities are the only way to feed back the results and impact generated in a comprehensive mid-term report (M18) and a final report (M30). To this purpose, a table will be created (Figure 17) that will be used to quantify the performance of the C&D in global terms and its validation of success. These reports will contribute into the realization of D5.6 and D5.7 reports by BRGM, by providing data and metrics of the C&D impacts.

 MADITRACE					
Final report of C&D impact					
Channel	Description	KPIs to measure impact	Target audience	Measurement of KPIs	Valuation of output
Website					
Social media accounts					
Press Bureau					
E-newsletters					
Events					
E-learning activities					
External event attendance					
Scientific and other publications					

Figure 28: Final report of C&D impact

10 Conclusion

Communication and dissemination activities are essential impact-boosting measures of any project. The plan presented here is a detailed strategy that will be strictly applied to promote MaDiTraCe and its results. This document brings together MaDiTraCe's communication and dissemination strategy to boost the project's presence by using different media and communication tools effectively. It should also serve as a reference to ensure consistency of messages according to the objectives and channels implemented.

The plan will be updated, adapted, and improved according to the monitoring results collected to achieve the desired impact. This document is a guideline to optimise the efforts of all project partners.